

SCIENTIFIC – THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE EDITING PROCESS

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Abstract: *This article examines editing, types of editing, specific aspects of certain types of literature, and the editor's role in perfecting the work.*

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The editorial stage of the publishing process begins after the author's manuscript is approved by the publisher and ends with its submission to the production department. At this stage, the manuscript is first evaluated by the department head, editor, or literary officer. The content of the manuscript - relevance of the topic, audience, objectivity, logic, reasonableness, reliability of facts, structure of the work - the structure of the manuscript, size, character of expression, language and style of the work, and its composition are evaluated.

After completing the evaluation stage of the manuscript, the editor writes a working review on it and can send it for external review [1, P–9]. Through a review, a specialist evaluates the work, recognizes its achievements, and separately notes shortcomings and defects.

After the author corrects the errors and omissions identified by the editor (if he agrees to these corrections), the editor begins work on the manuscript. The editor rereads the manuscript several times. During the first reading, the manuscript is not edited; basic notes are made and it is determined what type of editing will be applied to the text.

During the second reading, corrections are made to the composition, logical inaccuracies are corrected, and the type of editing is determined. After this, editing will be completed.

The composition of the work may generally have the following disadvantages:

1. Avoiding the topic.

An example of a deviation from the topic can be cited from the book “Language and Expression in Journalism”: ... In this sense, a journalist is, on the one hand, a representative of the interests of the state, and on the other hand, he is a representative of the interests of the people in the state press. It should be said that the strength and

prosperity of any country are created by the creative work of the people. Therefore, creating the well-being of the people is the main task of the state and government [2].

The first paragraph of the text mentions the personality of the journalist, but in the next part the author compares journalists with preachers in the Roman Empire, and in the following parts of the text thoughts about the ancient era continue. The author tells a long and detailed story about the Roman Empire and deviates far from the main topic. Errors in other parts of the book indicate that insufficient attention was paid to this situation in the editing.

1. Do not connect one thought with another. In this case, the editor is faced with the task of restoring logical connections in the text, making them understandable not only to the editor, but also to the reader. One of the most used techniques for restoring a logical connection between parts of a text is the use of introductory words and linking sentences.

2. Unsystematic expression.

3. Repetition of thoughts, sentences and quotes.

For example, in Yusuf Khamdamov's book "The Criterion of Development" we see a striking example of the repetition of ideas: Usually, when we think of journalism, the media comes to mind. Journalism means public information and is intended for a wide audience [3].

In the example above, two consecutive sentences have similar content, and removing one of them does not harm the content of the book.

1. Incorrect division into paragraphs.

K.I. Belinsky identifies four main types of editing: proofreading, reduction, processing and recycling.

Reading and correction. In this type, the task of the editor is to read the text, compare it with the author's handwriting, and correct obvious technical errors.

According to K.I. Belinsky, the following texts are usually read and corrected:

1. Official texts (decisions, decrees and orders, statements of the government, parliament and other official organizations, etc.).

2. Reprinted socio-political and artistic works (if they are reprinted without additions).

3. Definitive texts/republished definitive texts (definitivus - Latin. clear, completed, established), - texts that must fully correspond to the original text (constitution, text of laws, codes, contract, text of agreements and etc.).

4. Historical documents.

In the process of proofreading, spelling errors that do not change the content of the text, technical errors (such as the replacement of letters, merging with each other) are corrected, explanations of abbreviations are given, the title page of the publication is changed, if necessary, it is added to the book. a new preface can be written.

Abbreviation. In this process, the editor should shorten the author's text without harming its content. In this type of editing, scissors are cut directly to the text, not letters or technical errors. For this reason, when shortening, the editor should take into account the syntactic structure and content of the text.

Two types of reduction are used in editing practice. The first is to remove individual parts that make the text heavy and difficult, such as examples, facts, and personal information. In this case, the editor will have to check that the removed parts are not mentioned again in another part of the text, and that the paragraphs that fell out next to each other after editing are connected to each other.

The second type of truncation is in-text, and is used when it is not possible to remove a large part of the text. In this case, some words, sentences and sentences in this section may be removed.

Circumstances in which reduction is required:

1. Selecting a book of a certain size. Editors working on reference and encyclopedic publications usually face the task of reducing text to a certain number of pages or characters.

2. A reduction that eliminates shortcomings of the text. The most common shortcomings of the text are unnecessary repetitions, overloading of the text with the same type of facts and examples, small details, a large introduction explaining the obvious, and a large number of drawings.

After the text has been abbreviated, it is subject to review and approval by the author.

Processing. This is the most common type of editing, and in this process, the editor performs extensive editing work. In this case, the factual information in the text, the correction of inaccuracies in the composition, the correction of logical errors, and

the correcting of the linguistic and methodological tools of the text are performed. All corrections made to the manuscript must be approved by the author. If the author does not agree with the changes in it, it is enough to correct only the errors that do not correspond to the language standards in the text.

Recycling. It is a special type of editing, which is used when working on the works of authors who have not mastered the rules of spelling and literary language.

As with all types of editing, it is necessary to preserve the author's own style, but it is also worth mentioning the difficulty of achieving this when the text is completely reworked.

Today, the editor of a publishing house performs synthetic editing, that is, a process that combines all of the above types. A skilled editor can use different editing methods for different parts of the text, keeping in mind his main task - to change the text as little as possible and not to damage it. Which type of editing to use often depends on the type of work being edited. Today, publications are different in terms of content and form. Zoir Tahirov divides them into four types based on their main characteristics:

- according to its composition;
- according to the nature of the signs;
- according to periodicity and structure;
- according to the purpose and description of the data.

According to the structure of publishing products, they can be divided into such publications as leaflets, books, magazines, and (posters, booklets, newspapers, etc.).

According to the uniqueness of the symbol system, it is divided into textual, notational, map, image, and others.

Depending on the periodization, publication products are divided into different types (periodical-continuous, non-periodical publications) and, according to their structure, a collection of works, a series, a one-time publication collection, etc.

It is an important type of publication according to its purpose and description of information, and it is the following: scientific, scientific-popular, official, educational, public-political, reference, literary-artistic, technical release, advertising, press releases.

In addition to those mentioned above, publications can be distinguished according to who they are intended for (for children, teenagers and the blind).

Each publication, regardless of its type, undergoes the above-mentioned types of editing - proofreading, shortening, processing and, in some cases, recycling.

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